

THE BASIS OF APPLIED ART OF PAINTING

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Annotation

This article provides extensive information on the history of the art of painting, its place in applied art, its application as a major art form.

Keywords: Pattern, Painting, applied arts

To see aspects of the world that ordinary people can not see is peculiar only to artists! They show such things in the works they create! Such beauty is characteristic of the Kokand pattern, which by creating it and glorifying the world!

After finishing the Second World War, returning home, rubbing the soil of our homeland into the Eyes, Living with the enthusiasm to continue the “decoration” of the profession of their ancestors, the Master Saidahmad Mahmudov, who set himself the goal of becoming a propagandist of beauty, was born in the family of “Hunarmand” embroiderers in the city of Kokand in 1909. His father, Saidmahmud Nurkoziyev, studied the art of embroidery in his childhood and got the secret of mastery.

In the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people, folk decorative arts have been a key part of our cultural heritage. The types of applied arts that originated and flourished in the Uzbek land are world-famous for their uniqueness and uniqueness. Reflecting on this stage of development, we can see that the origin of Uzbek applied decorative art dates back to the earliest period of mankind, that is, the period of primitive society.

Archaeological excavations in the country testify to the fact that the creation of artifacts by the human body began in the Stone Age and has been going on for centuries.

We have the material evidence of the primitive community system - tools of labor and hunting, furniture and ornaments, the remains of human settlements. Underground historical monuments, human and animal remains, paintings and reliefs on snow and basement walls are important sources for studying the history of primitive society.

During the Paleolithic period, examples of applied and decorative arts began to spread. Archaeologists are still struggling to gather enough evidence before reaching the final conclusions about the origin of artefacts. The sedentary nature of people, the observation of the laws of nature, led to an increase in the sense of

symmetry, rhythm, form. He created a unique art of painting, which is based on the smooth repetition or interweaving of the same elements. Painting became widespread in the New Stone Age (Neolithic), influenced and contributed to the development of decorative and applied arts. Decorating pottery and other items with patterns became widespread. Parallel, spiral and wavy lines, circles form the basis of many patterns of this period. Geometric patterns were gradually enriched with schematic drawings from the world of man, animals, and plants, and expanded in content. Its elements continued to reflect the symbolic signs of the cosmic forces. For example, a socket is a symbol of the sun, a wavy line is a symbol of movement, a symbol of water, and so on.

The art of painting now not only serves a decorative function, but also expresses the Rocky and philosophical concepts of the people.

During the Bronze Age, pottery flourished in Central Asia. The advent of pottery made the artwork more elegant and beautiful. The red background found in Chust is notable for its pottery with black paintings and patterns.

Decorative and applied arts also play a leading role in the Iron Age. In addition to geometric patterns in decoration, the use of plot compositions is especially developed.

Various examples of decorative and applied arts, weapons of war, hunting and labor, found underground and in tombs, also play an important role in the study of the art and culture of ancient Central Asia. The ceramics are made of bronze, gold, and silver, and the surface of the utensils is decorated with patterns, embossed images, and sculptures. Some objects reflect real-life events. These factual materials serve to understand the art and culture of the past, the aesthetic and artistic views of the people.

It is known from archeological excavations in Uzbekistan that the art of painting developed in Khorezm, Sogd, Bactria and other regions. Remains of paintings and patterns found in the excavations of the Buddhist temples of Fayoztepa (I-II centuries), Dalvarzintepa (I-century) in Surkhandarya region are a clear proof of this.

The "Amudarya Rich" (Ox Rich), discovered by the upper reaches of the Amudarya, plays an important role in understanding the artistic life and culture of Central Asia in the IV-VI centuries BC. These monuments, now housed in the British Museum in London, include gold statues, various jugs, bracelets, rings, seals, coins, gold chariots and weapons.

Alexander the Great (Alexander the Great) defeated the Achaemenid Empire in the 4th century BC and conquered much of Central Asia. Only the nomadic tribes of Khorezm, Fergana and Syrdarya retained their independence.

As a result of such a deep philosophical approach to applied art, the creation of works of art based on conditionality, stylization and symbolism has intensified. This historical factor has given impetus to the rapid development of the Uzbek national decorative art, and our world-famous architectural monuments testify to the wonderful harmony and integration of plaster, tile, painting, calligraphy, stone carving and other arts. Folk applied decorative art enriches the spiritual world of people, forms their artistic taste, nurtures their psyche. That is why the Uzbek folk applied art is one of the most important sources in the artistic, moral, universal education of people, in the formation of their scientific worldview, as well as in raising their cultural level.

In the recent past, the most developed types of Uzbek applied decorative art, such as painting, pottery, stone and bone carving, carving, knife-making, weaving, jewelry, embroidery, goldsmithing, carpet weaving, felt-making, basket-making unique performance technologies, real national names, unique terms, schools, styles specific to these arts, and the services of renowned masters in these fields are known all over the world.

The art of painting in Central Asia has long been known around the world. The magnificent buildings built by our ancestors in the past have not lost their charm to this day. The tastefully crafted patterns still amaze us. The pattern is an Arabic image, meaning a flower, and is an ornament created by repeating in a certain order the bird, the animal, the flora, the geometric and various other shapes.

As a result of following the requirements of Islam, the depiction of animals, birds, and people disappeared and painting flourished. The Arabic script has been mastered. The result was an epigraphic style with patterns. The Arabic script was drawn along with the patterns. The Arabic script served as both an ornament and a blessing.

Painting as an art form has long been an important part of Uzbek culture. Over the centuries, his artistic traditions have emerged and developed. Unlike all other forms of art, the patterns show the interdependence of generations, the continuity of national traditions. The tradition of painting has been passed down from grandfather to father and from father to son as a method of studying this type of art. Because of this, the art of painting has survived to the present day. The best examples of the pattern are distinguished by the purposefulness and

beauty of the forms combined by a rich creative imagination. This reflects the difference in the views of folk masters on the environment. The game of patterned drawing, like the melody in music, is composed of "a great generalization of the people's life experience," such as song and fairy tale.

Art painting is the art of creating beauty in a combination of colors and unique compositions. In his work, the artist skillfully uses the natural brilliance and harmony of colors, beautiful shapes, textures of materials to achieve a bright expression.

In the traditional architecture of Uzbekistan, painting is mainly used to decorate ceilings, silent vodkas, palace pillars, mosques, schools, houses of the rich, and wooden objects. The rhythmic movement of intertwined twigs, branches and luxuriously depicted flowers in delicate floral-geometric patterns, the Islamic motifs in the works of Uzbek masters and the classical motifs of girih patterns are adapted to the shape of the ceilings. The pattern serves to decorate more interiors and covered porches and porches.

Today, the pattern is used in architecture, home furnishings, gifts, small wooden toys, musical instruments, and household items.

The art of painting is gaining momentum today. Through the press, radio, television, and cinema, people become acquainted with these works of art and their folk masters. Among these artists are O. Kasimjanov, Ye. Raufov, A. Boltaev, S. Norkuziyev, A. Azimov, A. Isayev, B. Abdullayev, T. Tukhtahojayev, J. Khakimov, Z. Basitkhanov. , M.Turaev, T.Akhmedov, K.Karimov, A.Illkhomov and others. The works of our national masters and their students are exhibited in the Museum of Applied Arts in Tashkent, exhibition halls, art salons, as well as in residential and public buildings, such as the Tashkent State Circus, Alisher Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater, National Academic can be seen in administrative and residential buildings such as the Drama Theater, the Museum of the History of the Timurids, the buildings of the Oliy Majlis and the City Hall, metro stations, hotels. The task is to expand the network of clubs in schools and out-of-school institutions as much as possible. The study of folk art helps to develop students' artistic taste, diligence and a number of useful knowledge and skills. Helps to identify and develop their creative abilities..

Использованная литература:

1. Ortiqboy, S. S., & Makhsudali, J. (2022). A Desire Sung in a Pattern. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN, 3(5), 6-9.
2. Prozorova, M. N., Zharkov, A. D., Zharkova, A. A., Khamdamova, V. A., Sattorova, S. O., & Losev, V. S. (2021). University graduate career potential

- in digital transformation period: Features and problems of formation. Linguistics and Culture Review, 5(S3), 1574-1585.
3. Sattorova, S. O. (2021). PATTERN SUNG ON THE CARPET. Экономика и социум, (5-1), 445-448.
 4. Abdurahimovich, M. A., & Qizi, S. S. O. (2020). Master Student Etiquette. www.conferencepublication.com, 22.
 5. Khaydarovich, A. A. (2020). Colors in Descriptive Art. International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development, 2(12), 20-22.
 6. Mamadjanivich, B. B. IT is Necessary to Feed the World with Beauty!. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(8), 215-217.
 7. Baratboyev Batir Mamadjanivich, Sattorova Sarvinoz Ortiqboy Qizi International Journal on Integrated Education page 215-217, Publishing 2020
<https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE/article/view/566>
 8. S.Bulatov "O'zbek xalq amaliy bezak san'ati" Toshkent-2004y.
 9. X. Rafiqova "Ferganski rospis" Toshkent-2006.y.

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**WORLD
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